

Iso Electric Point (IEP)

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 128.**

IsoElectric Point- Z potential SOP

A 10g/L stock dispersion was prepared by dispersing NM powder in HPW. Then a 100 mg/L NM dispersion in 1 mM NaNO₃ at pH 11 was prepared by adding 200 uL of NM stock dispersion in the NaNO₃ basic (NaOH) solution. Dispersion (20 mL in a 50 mL centrifuge PP tube) was sonicate 30 min in a sonication bath (120 W nominal). Then the dispersion was titrated from basic (11) to acidic (3) pH by adding HNO₃ and let the system stabilized for 20 min between each acid addition (each ELS measurement)